

Utilisation of fly ash in insulating castable refractory

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Utilisation of fly ash as a raw material for making insulating castable refractory has been explored. The fly ash mixed with other raw material like kyanite, plastic clay, calcined alumina and saw dust has been fired to develop insulating aggregates. These aggregate are utilised for castable refractory using high alumina cement.

Fly ash contains generally a high percentage of alumina and silica present in various forms¹. Because of its high silica and alumina content, fly ash may prove to be a potential raw material in refractory and ceramic industries. Insulation in high temperature is very vital as it leads to energy saving. In refractory industries, unshaped insulating castable refractories are gaining more and more importance because of certain advantages, such as low processing cost, ease of applications and superior performance over conventional refractories². Although researches on the development of insulating refractory materials from fly ash have been attempted³, little attention has so far been paid on the development of insulating unshaped castables from fly ash. Keeping this in perspective, the present work was undertaken to explore the feasibility of making insulating castable refractory using fly ash so that naturally occurring aluminosilicate minerals can be preserved.

Results and Discussion

Fly ash is a non-plastic and alumina-deficient material from the point of view of making castable refractory, and as such, various other raw materials are needed. Depending on the applications, various formulations were tried. The raw materials selected for the study (Table 1) have different properties which have been exploited for making the insulating

aggregates. Kyanite, besides being a rich source of alumina, undergoes phenomenal increase in volume⁴ (about 16%) on heating causing a reduction in density and an increase in porosity of the aggregates and as such, has been specifically used. Calcined alumina has been added for increasing the refractoriness of the aggregates. Plastic clay provides the necessary green strength. China clay is commonly used to impart strength (both dry and fired) to the refractory materials. Fly ash has been used in various proportions in the batches, as shown in Table 2. Different methods have been

Table 2. Composition of mixtures for various batches before firing

Raw material	% Composition of the batches			
	I	II	III	IV
Kyanite	20	20	20	20
Plastic clay	10	10	10	10
China clay	0	20	40	60
Fly ash	60	40	20	0
Calcined alumina	10	10	10	10
Saw dust (parts)	35	35	35	35

reported by Clemets⁵ for achieving insulation by generating porosity, out of which the use of combustibles is probably the earliest and most widely used one. Saw dust, being the cheapest as well as easily available combustible, has been used in the present investigation. The physical properties of the aggregates so formed are detailed in Table 3. It can be seen that as the fly ash content decreases (or the clay content increases), the bulk density increases and porosity decreases. This might be due to the fact that the extent of solid state sintering in batches containing higher propor-

Table 1. Chemical composition of the raw materials

Comp.	Fly ash	Kyanite	Plastic clay	China clay	Calcined alumina	Cement
SiO ₂	61.57	35.63	54.80	43.75	0.02	5.60
Al ₂ O ₃	26.33	59.42	28.60	36.45	99.40	49.88
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.35	1.21	1.50	1.25	0.04	3.80
TiO ₂	2.09	0.78	2.50	1.85	-	6.90
CaO	0.94	-	1.34	1.65	-	32.30
MgO	0.84	-	0.07	0.09	-	-
Na ₂ O	0.85	-	0.32	0.30	-	-
K ₂ O	0.35	-	0.65	0.20	-	-
LOI	0.73	2.40	10.20	14.70	0.20	0.50

Table 3. Properties of fired aggregates batches I-IV

Aggregate	I	II	III	IV
Bulk density (g ml ⁻¹)	0.68	0.74	0.82	0.89
Apparent porosity (%)	62.3	58.4	53.9	47.5

tion of fly ash compared to clay is poor. Fly ash is a product of combustion and probably due to this its surface activity towards thermal reaction is less than that of clay minerals. It is, therefore, expected that aggregates containing higher proportion of fly ash (compared to clay minerals) will possess more voids in the structure. From the XRD diagrams of the aggregates it was observed that all the batches contain mullite, quartz, cristoballite and corundum as the major crystalline phases.

For the sake of better packing of particles in the castable refractory, the aggregates were sized to fractions of 1-5 mm and <1 mm. The batch composition was the following: aggregate 1-5 mm, 50%; aggregate <1 mm, 25%; high alumina cement, 25%. The cement employed in this case had the purpose of providing green strength at room temperature as well as maintaining the strength during drying and firing. The properties of the castable refractories are detailed in Table 4. In all the batches the compressive strength decreased at 800 and 1100° (compared to that at 110°). The strength further increased at 1300°. This might be due to the breaking of cement binder at 800° and the starting of the development of ceramic bonds at intermedi-

110° will be 1440. The shrinkage is found to increase in the batches with lesser fly ash content. This may be attributed to further desnification in the batches as a result of more interaction between the aggregates and the cement.

It is seen that gain in insulation has been achieved at the cost of compressive strength. Therefore, to obtain a tailor made refractory, an optimum percentage of fly ash can be utilised so that it has enough strength and insulating property.

Experimental

Fly ash was collected from Farakka Super Thermal Power Station, West Bengal, India. The various other raw materials utilised were: (i) plastic clay of Birbhum, West Bengal, (ii) raw kyanite of Bihar Mineral Development Corporation, (iii) calcined alumina of Indian Aluminium Co., Calcutta, (iv) china clay of Rajmahal of Bihar, (v) high alumina cement of Maithan Ceramics Ltd., Bihar and (vi) saw dust from local source. The composition analyses of the ash and the other raw materials were done following standard conventional procedures ASTM C573.

The mixtures of raw materials were pelletized and the pellets were fired at 1350° for 3 h. The characteristics of the fired aggregates such as bulk density and apparent porosity were measured following ASTM C134 method. In the next stage, high alumina cement was mixed with the aggregates after crushing them to two different size fractions, viz. 1-5 mm and <1 mm. To evaluate the performance of the castables, the materials were vibrocasted in 160/40/40 mm moulds after mixing with required quantity of water. The cast bodies were first kept in a humid chamber for a period of 24 h at a relative humidity of 90% and then dried at 110° for 24 h. Then the bodies were fired at three different temperature, 800, 1100 and 1300° for a period of 2 h. Thermal conductivity was measured with pre-fired hot face of the castable blocks at 500° as per ASTM C417. The linear shrinkage of the castables was measured by firing at 1260° for 5 h following ASTM C401-89.

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Table 4. Dry density and thermal conductivities of the castable refractories

Batch no.	Dry density kg m ⁻³	Cold crushing strength kg cm ⁻²				Thermal cond. kcal m ⁻¹ h ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	%Linear shrinkage
		110°	800°	1100°	1300°		
I	1115	36	27	29	42	0.34	0.79
II	1335	52	33	35	57	0.39	0.96
III	1425	88	43	47	48.5	0.41	1.05
IV	1567	93	67	65	76	0.47	1.27

ate temperatures and compression of the ceramic bond formation at elevated temperatures (i.e. at 1300°). Castables prepared with higher percentage of ash showed less thermal conductivity and compressive strength compared to those of china clay – based castables. The decrease of conductivity, and hence decrease of insulation, is a consequence of higher porosity generated with higher percentage of ash. The bonding between the aggregates and the cement is poor in batches containing higher percentage of fly ash. This is responsible for low compressive strength. Reference to ASTM classification on castable refractories (C401-89) reveals that the bulk density as well as linear shrinkage after firing of dried castable refractories made with fly ash conforms to class Q which states that the permanent linear shrinkage should not be more than 1.5% when fired for 5 h at 1260° and maximum bulk density (kg m⁻³) after drying at 105–

Note

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